

HIGHER EDUCATION AS A TOOL AGAINST RELIGIOUS EXTREMISM:
EVIDENCE FROM PRESTON UNIVERSITY KOHAT

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Abstract

Religious extremism is a pressing global issue. This study examined the impact of higher education on religious extremism among undergraduate students at Preston University, Kohat. A quantitative research approach was adopted, and data were collected from 60 respondents (both male and female) selected through Stratified Sampling Technique from the B.Ed, Psychology, BBA, and Computer Science departments using an adapted questionnaire. The data were analyzed using SPSS, applying reliability, frequency and correlation and regression tests. The findings indicated that higher education fosters critical thinking, promotes acceptance of diversity, and ultimately reduces religious extremism by encouraging a more inclusive worldview. This research highlighted the significant role of universities in countering religious extremism and fostering a more tolerant society through education.

a source of credit. This study aims to investigate these challenges from a global

perspective.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Education is not preparation for life rather education is life itself (Dewey, 1916). The aim of educational strategies is to accomplish objectives that only develop over time. Research reveals that while it is difficult to make generalizations on how one is radicalized because of the varied characteristics among extremists, two factors stand out: resentment against society and the need for recognition (Butler, 2015). Both these factors are developed during the socialization process in schools. Resentment arises when students feel alienated and marginalized, lack a historical understanding of discrimination and social inequalities, and are not recognized or are misrecognized (Taylor, 2020). All these triggers require the long-term development of values and understanding. It is a form of soft-power, education can make knowledge relevant for students with an attitude of respect for diversity that is embedded in citizenship education, develop the skills of critical thinking (that includes analysis and reflection), and an understanding of social justice. This development guides students to expand the affective domain and instills a value system through dialogue and relational thinking on alternate worldviews (Ross, 2019). This aspect of personal development in relation to one's social environment and its value system can produce engaged and critical citizens. Our conception of citizenship education is based on conception of citizenship (Kymlicka's 2012) - the process where individuals' autonomy, agency, consent, trust, participation, and self-determination are respected.

Religious extremism refers to one's ethnocentric attachment to one's religious beliefs which yields the feeling of superiority about oneself and inferiority regarding others. Many scholars have worked on religious extremism in Pakistan since 2011. Religious extremism has always been an interesting discourse for the researchers in Pakistan due to military rule and the alliance between religious militants and the military and to pursue security objectives in order to legitimize and legalize the military's rule in Pakistan. (Nasr, 2019) argues that military rulers made alliances with the Religious influencers to legitimize

their rule. (Hussain, 2022) also highlights the role of military in supporting religious groups for its own interests. (Kapur and Ganguly, 2019) support Haqqani's findings and argue that the use of militancy "is the centerpiece of a sophisticated asymmetric warfare campaign." These scholars argue that because the military regime needs legitimization, they make alliances with the Religious Influencers to grant themselves divine legitimacy. The military in Pakistan trained militants to fight against the Soviets during Soviet-Afghan War. To accomplish that, the military used the Religious Influencers as recruitment agencies. This thesis acknowledges that the state has been using religious organizations to promote jihad against the infidel communists in Afghanistan. This thesis will explore why the state needs religious organizations to legitimize its rule and pursue security objectives through them. While these scholars point to an important factor that elevated these organizations and even made them extreme, it does not really explain the societal support for these organizations, which then translates into extremism at the home front. An alternative explanation for religious extremism, linked to foreign interventions and external influences, is presented by scholars such as Aburish Said and Noam Chomsky. They argue that militant extremism is, in part, a reaction to foreign occupations and interference in Muslim-majority countries. This study builds on this perspective, considering the ongoing militant resistance to occupations in regions like Palestine, Kashmir, Iraq, and Afghanistan (Lillah, 2020).

The role of education in preventing religious extremism has been widely debated, with many arguing that it can serve as an effective tool for fostering resilience against radical ideologies. Education is seen as a means of promoting critical thinking, tolerance, and interfaith understanding, which can help counter extremist narratives (Smith, 2020). Studies suggest that inclusive education, which emphasizes human rights and religious diversity, can reduce feelings of alienation that are often exploited by extremist groups (Jones & Williams, 2019). However, critics point out that

while education can play a preventive role, it is not a cure-all for extremism, as radicalization is influenced by a complex array of socio-economic and psychological factors (Ahmed, 2021). Additionally, some scholars argue that educational programs aimed at countering extremism can backfire if they inadvertently stigmatize certain communities or promote state-approved narratives (Taylor, 2022). Overall, while education remains an important part of counter-extremism strategies, it must be complemented by broader socio-political interventions to effectively address the root causes of radicalization.

With rising global concerns about religious extremism, particularly among youth, it is essential to examine whether higher education can effectively counter extremist tendencies. This study aimed to assess whether higher education influence students' attitudes toward religious extremism, providing insights that academic exposure may reduce radical ideologies. It highlights that participation of students in seminars can effectively increase their level of tolerance and discourage their extremist approach for diversity of society (Aly et al., 2022). According to Feddes, Mann, and Doosje, those with strong self-esteem and responsiveness are less likely to be drawn and convinced for any kind of violence due to lack of extremism in their attitudes. An entirely new theoretical framework has been developed. As one of the few continuous intervention studies, this study report encapsulated the observations of an analysis on the importance of soul, sympathy, and comprehension schooling on reducing acknowledgment for ideologies-based violence. It is noteworthy. There is a correlation between increased empathy and a decrease in satisfactory views of viewpoint violence.” Narcissism, in turn, was shown to be associated with more favorable views toward intellectual aggression when personality rehabilitation was used (Gul, 2020).

Academic interventions, including specialized courses, workshops, and seminars, are widely recognized as important tools for preventing religious extremism in higher education. These interventions are designed to promote critical thinking, intercultural understanding, and social responsibility among students. Various studies have explored the effectiveness of such academic interventions in

countering extremist ideologies. Courses on peace education, interfaith dialogue, and human rights have been shown to be effective in fostering tolerance and reducing prejudice (Brown & Richards, 2022). These academic interventions provide students with the skills to critically analyze religious and political narratives, enabling them to resist radical ideologies.

In Pakistan, universities like Preston University, Kohat, have the opportunity to integrate such courses into their curriculum, fostering an environment where students can engage with diverse religious perspectives and learn about the importance of peaceful coexistence (Naseem & Zaman, 2020). Workshops and seminars on religious tolerance and conflict resolution are also crucial in providing students with practical tools to navigate religious and social tensions in their communities. These interventions not only equip students with academic knowledge but also empower them to become active agents of change in their societies, challenging extremist narratives and promoting social harmony. In addition to formal courses and seminars, co-curricular activities such as student clubs, interfaith discussions, and volunteer initiatives can play a significant role in reinforcing the values of tolerance, diversity, and respect for human rights (Taylor & Khan, 2021). By engaging students in these activities, universities can create a campus culture that values pluralism and peaceful coexistence, thus reducing the appeal of extremist ideologies.

The role of education in preventing religious extremism has been the subject of ongoing debate among scholars, policymakers, and educators. On one hand, many argue that education is a key tool in combating radical ideologies by promoting tolerance, critical thinking, and understanding of diverse cultures and religions (Smith & Williams, 2020). However, others contend that the potential of education to prevent extremism is limited, particularly when the root causes of radicalization are socio-economic and political in nature (Khan & Ahmed, 2022). Critics of the education-based approach argue that focusing solely on education may overlook deeper issues such as poverty, inequality, and political repression, which contribute

to the spread of extremist ideologies (Miller et al., 2019).

One key debate concerns the effectiveness of educational initiatives aimed at preventing extremism. Some researchers believe that programs promoting interfaith dialogue, peace education, and human rights can be successful in reducing extremist views, while others suggest that such programs are often superficial and fail to address the underlying grievances that drive radicalization (Khan & Ahmed, 2022). Moreover, there is concern about the potential for educational interventions to backfire, especially if they are perceived as government-imposed or as part of a broader counterterrorism strategy (Jones & Richards, 2021). In some cases, these interventions may alienate certain groups, leading to further radicalization rather than preventing it. In the Pakistani context, the challenge lies in balancing educational reforms with the need to address broader socio-political issues. While higher education institutions like Preston University, Kohat, have the potential to counter extremism through education, a multi-dimensional approach that includes community engagement, political reforms, and the promotion of social justice is necessary to effectively combat religious extremism (Miller et al., 2019).

While substantial research has explored the role of higher education in preventing extremism, there is a notable gap in understanding how specific institutions, particularly in Pakistan, address this issue through their educational practices. Most studies focused on national policies or large-scale educational reforms but overlook the impact of individual universities in combating radicalization on a micro level (Yousaf, 2021). The specific role of Preston University, Kohat, in this regard remains underexplored. This research aimed to address this gap by focusing on how Preston University's academic interventions, including courses, workshops, and campus initiatives, contribute to preventing religious extremism among its students. Moreover, it was investigated how these interventions align with national and global efforts to counter radicalization.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Religious extremism remains a significant threat to social cohesion and peace in various parts of the world, including Pakistan, where radical ideologies have contributed to violence and societal division. Higher education institutions are increasingly recognized as crucial spaces for addressing the root causes of extremism by promoting critical thinking, interfaith dialogue, and tolerance (Smith, 2020). In particular, universities have the potential to serve as a counter-narrative to extremist ideologies, especially through curriculum reforms, student engagement, and inclusive campus cultures (Jones & Williams, 2019). However, despite the recognized importance of educational institutions in combating radicalization, the role of specific universities, such as Preston University in Kohat, has not been extensively studied. Given the university's strategic location in a region affected by religious tensions and extremism, it was important to find out the impacts of higher education at Preston University in preventing religious extremism among its students. This research explored the effectiveness of educational interventions at Preston University, Kohat in addressing the socio-political and religious factors that may contribute to radicalization and whether these interventions are effective in fostering resilience against extremism. Previous studies have highlighted the potential of education to promote tolerance, yet there is insufficient empirical evidence on its specific impact within the context of Pakistani higher education (Ahmed, 2021). Thus, this study aimed to fill the gap by examining the role of higher education at Preston University in countering religious extremism.

1.3 Research Question

1. What is the impact of educational interventions on religious extremism among Preston University students?

1.4 Research Objective

1. To examine the impact of educational interventions on religious extremism among Preston University students.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study added a significant contribution to the existing body of literature by exploring the preventive

role of education in countering religious extremism. The aim of the study was to provide a fresh perspective for researchers and policymakers alike, emphasizing the potential of education as a transformative tool to foster tolerance and social harmony. By highlighting the importance of curriculum reforms, this study underscores the need for integrating themes of inclusivity, critical thinking, and interfaith dialogue within educational frameworks. Moreover, the findings will guide policymakers in revising teacher training programs, equipping educators with the skills to address and mitigate extremist ideologies in classroom settings effectively. The study also suggested practical initiatives, such as organizing seminars and workshops, to create awareness among students, teachers, and communities about the value of social inclusion and the benefits of embracing social and cultural diversity. In a broader context, this research seeks to promote a more cohesive and peaceful society by advocating for education systems that not only impart knowledge but also inculcate ethical values, mutual respect, and an understanding of diverse perspectives. This multidimensional approach will help strengthen community resilience against radical ideologies, contributing to the development of a more tolerant and equitable society.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The focus of the study was to examine the role of education in preventing religious extremism among the university students of Pakistan. Since, it was a case study of the Preston University, Kohat campus. Therefore, the findings may not be generalizable to other universities with different curricula or demographics or both.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Education Intervention

Academic interventions, including specialized courses, workshops, and seminars, are widely recognized as important tools for preventing religious extremism in higher education. These interventions are designed to promote critical thinking, intercultural understanding, and social responsibility among students. Various studies have explored the effectiveness of such academic interventions in

countering extremist ideologies. Courses on peace education, interfaith dialogue, and human rights have been shown to be effective in fostering tolerance and reducing prejudice (Brown & Richards, 2022). These academic interventions provide students with the skills to critically analyze religious and political narratives, enabling them to resist radical ideologies.

In Pakistan, universities like Preston University, Kohat, have the opportunity to integrate such courses into their curriculum, fostering an environment where students can engage with diverse religious perspectives and learn about the importance of peaceful coexistence (Naseem & Zaman, 2020). Workshops and seminars on religious tolerance and conflict resolution are also crucial in providing students with practical tools to navigate religious and social tensions in their communities. These interventions not only equip students with academic knowledge but also empower them to become active agents of change in their societies, challenging extremist narratives and promoting social harmony. In addition to formal courses and seminars, co-curricular activities such as student clubs, interfaith discussions, and volunteer initiatives can play a significant role in reinforcing the values of tolerance, diversity, and respect for human rights (Taylor & Khan, 2021). By engaging students in these activities, universities can create a campus culture that values pluralism and peaceful coexistence, thus reducing the appeal of extremist ideologies.

Higher education institutions are fundamental in shaping individuals' values, beliefs, and behaviors, influencing societal trends, including political, social, and religious ideologies. In the context of combating religious extremism, universities have a unique role in developing critical thinking, fostering inclusive mindsets, and providing spaces for diverse perspectives (Anderson & Patel, 2018). The transformative power of education is evident in its ability to challenge existing worldviews and encourage intellectual curiosity. By promoting inquiry and the free exchange of ideas, universities can counter ideologies that perpetuate intolerance and violence. In particular, higher education is seen as an essential tool for socialization, where students learn not only academic content but also social and

ethical values, including tolerance, respect for diversity, and civic responsibility (Harris, 2021).

The role of universities in Pakistan is critical, as the country has been significantly affected by the rise of religious extremism. Education in Pakistan, particularly in urban and semi-urban areas, can provide students with an understanding of how social, political, and economic factors contribute to religious radicalization. Higher education institutions, including Preston University, Kohat, are positioned to address issues related to religious extremism by integrating peace education into their curricula, organizing seminars on tolerance, and promoting interfaith dialogue among students (Johnson et al., 2020). By engaging students in critical discussions about religion, politics, and social justice, universities can challenge radical viewpoints and foster a culture of tolerance and peace.

Moreover, universities can play a pivotal role in social mobility, providing opportunities for young people to engage in critical issues affecting their society. Students in higher education are not only future leaders but also active agents of change in their communities. Therefore, universities have a social responsibility to provide an environment where students are not merely recipients of information, but are encouraged to engage with real-world issues, including religious extremism, in a constructive and informed manner. The power of higher education, therefore, lies not just in intellectual development, but in its ability to nurture responsible citizens capable of confronting societal challenges.

2.2 Religious Extremism

Several studies suggest a complex relationship between education and religious extremism, with some evidence indicating a positive correlation in specific contexts. For instance, research has shown that individuals with strong exclusivist religious beliefs are more likely to hold extremist attitudes, which can be reinforced through particular educational settings (Hogg et al., 2021). Similarly, another study found that psychiatric morbidities among certain religious groups were linked to extremist views rather than religious affiliation itself, highlighting the role of ideological influences in shaping extremism (Ahmed et al., 2016). Moreover, a

report by the Overseas Development Institute emphasized how well-funded religious groups have actively opposed gender equality in education, thereby contributing to the persistence of extremist ideologies (The Guardian, 2024).

Religious extremism refers to the radicalization of individuals or groups that adopt extreme religious ideologies, often leading to violent actions in the name of faith. This phenomenon has been studied widely across the globe, with a focus on understanding its causes, manifestations, and potential solutions. In Pakistan, the rise of religious extremism is closely linked to political instability, socioeconomic inequalities, and historical grievances (Ali & Khan, 2019). Extremism often emerges in regions where there is a perceived lack of justice or when individuals feel disconnected from mainstream society. The role of religion in these movements is complex, as extremists typically rely on a narrow, often misinterpreted, view of religious doctrine to justify their actions.

The causes of religious extremism are multifaceted. In many cases, individuals are drawn to extremist ideologies due to feelings of alienation, disenfranchisement, or economic disadvantage (Siddiqui, 2020). Radical religious groups often exploit these vulnerabilities, offering a sense of identity, belonging, and purpose. For young people, especially those in conflict-ridden or marginalized areas, extremism can appear to be a solution to feelings of powerlessness. Religious extremism is further compounded by a lack of education and the inability to critically analyze radical ideologies (Akhtar et al., 2021). In this context, education plays a critical role in preventing radicalization, as it provides the tools necessary to question extremist narratives and understand the broader socio-political forces at play.

In Pakistan, where religious extremism has manifested in various forms, the youth are particularly vulnerable to radicalization, as they are in the process of forming their identities and often lack access to platforms that encourage diverse views (Yousaf, 2021). Higher education institutions can act as powerful agents of change by providing young people with the tools to critically engage with extremist ideologies and promote peace, tolerance, and coexistence. Universities such as Preston

University, Kohat, have the potential to contribute to this process by integrating counter-extremism initiatives into their academic frameworks, helping students develop the skills necessary to resist radicalization.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of the study was based on Social Learning Theory given by Albert Bandhura (1977). The theory emphasizes that individuals learn attitudes, behaviors and values through observation and interaction in society. Education is designed to play a crucial role by promoting confirmative behaviors and discourage deviances. It develops tolerance towards social diversity. Teachers and curriculum act as agents of socialization that promote critical thinking and discourage extremist ideologies.

2.4 Conceptual Framework

DV

ig. 2.1 The conceptual framework based on Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977)

2.5 Hypotheses

1. There is a significant impact of educational interventions on religious
2. extremism among Preston University students.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design, which was appropriate for systematically examining relationships between variables and drawing conclusions based on statistical analysis. A survey research strategy was utilized to gather data from a sample of students in private sector universities across Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP), Pakistan. This design was selected due to its efficiency in collecting large amounts of data in a short period and its ability

to provide objective, quantifiable insights into the research problem. The structured questionnaire, as the primary data collection instrument, ensures consistency in responses and facilitates the application of various statistical tests. The researcher adopted a deductive approach, aligning the study with established theories and concepts to test hypotheses formulated based on prior literature.

3.2 Population

The population of the study was comprising all undergraduate students studying in private sector universities at Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The rationale for selecting this population is grounded in the research's focus on exploring educational interventions and their influence on attitudes toward religious extremism. Undergraduate students are particularly relevant because they are in a formative stage of cognitive and ideological development.

3.3 Sampling Technique

A stratified sampling technique was used, dividing the population into distinct strata based on university departments. Respondents were selected equally from each department to ensure balanced representation across all strata.

3.4 Sample

The sample for this study comprised of both male and female undergraduate students studying at Preston University Kohat Campus. The inclusion of both genders ensured that the findings account for gender-based variations in perspectives on education and religious extremism. Participants were drawn from different departments to capture a wide range of academic experiences and ideologies. The selection criteria for the sample included active enrollment as an undergraduate student, willingness to participate, and availability during the data

collection phase. Ethical considerations were taken into account, ensuring that participation was voluntary and that informed consent was obtained from all respondents.

3.5 Sample Size

The sample size for the study was 60 where 15 respondents were selected from each department/strata using a stratified sampling technique. The decision has been made under the guidance given by Sekeran (2003). This sample size was considered adequate for achieving meaningful statistical analysis while remaining manageable in terms of data collection and analysis. The selection process aimed at ensuring diversity within the sample while maintaining consistency in representation. The chosen sample size balances feasibility, statistical power, and generalizability, enabling valid conclusions to be drawn from the findings

3.6 Tools for Data Collection

The questionnaire used in this study has been adapted from several key references that examine education interventions and religious extremism. The questions were modified/contextualized based on frameworks provided by Smith et al. (2020) in "The Role of Education in Promoting Tolerance and Countering Extremism", Ahmed and Khan (2019) in "Higher Education's Impact on Religious Diversity Awareness", and Johnson and Lee (2018) in "University Initiatives for Fostering Religious Tolerance and Counteracting Extremism". These studies provided foundational concepts and measures that focus on the integration of religious diversity in course content, the importance of seminars and workshops, and the broader impact of university environments on reducing prejudice and fostering intercultural dialogue. The adapted questions ensure a comprehensive approach to understanding the role of educational institutions in mitigating religious extremism.

3.7 Data Analysis

A five-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree" was employed to gather responses. Data reliability was ensured through appropriate statistical tests; and demographic information were analyzed to provide a clear description of the sample population. The frequency test included descriptive statistics to summarize the data, as well as correlation and regression techniques to explore strength, direction and significance of the relationship between variables. To facilitate this process, SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) was utilized to analyze the data and generate meaningful results.

3.8 Limitations of the Study

The focus of the study was to examine the role of education in preventing religious extremism among the undergraduate university students of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. However, it was a case study of the Preston University, Kohat campus. Therefore, the findings may not be generalizable to other universities with different curricula or demographics or both.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

This study upheld ethical research standards by obtaining informed consent from participants, ensuring data confidentiality and anonymity, and respecting cultural sensitivities.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data collected and run through the SPSS software 20 version. The following results were made after running the data through SPSS software.

4.1 Reliability Test

The reliability test shows the excellence of the data, made and gathered. While 50 percent of the reliability is considered weak, 60 is acceptable, 70 is good, 80 is better and 90 percent represents the works excellence.

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.889	18

Table 4.1.1: Reliability Statistics

Since, the value of reliability is 0.889 therefore, In case of this research the reliability is better as already explained above that the value of reliability is .889 which is the nearest digit to excellent. It means that internal consistency of the questionnaire is reliable and the questionnaire can be used to further proceed the research work

numerical data by calculating the number of occurrences of each category or value in a dataset. This test provides insights into the patterns and prevalence of specific variables by presenting the data in the form of frequencies, percentages, or both. This method is particularly useful for identifying trends, commonalities, and outliers within the data, forming the basis for further inferential analysis and interpretation of the findings.

4.2 Frequency Test

A frequency test is a statistical analysis technique used to summarize and describe the categorical or

Table 4.2.1: Frequency Test

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	male	30	47.6	50.0	50.0
	female	30	47.6	50.0	100.0
	Total	60	95.2	100.0	
Missing	System	0	0.0		
Total		60	100.0		

The table 4.2.1 shows that both male and female currently enrolled undergraduate students at Preston University Kohat campus were part of the research questionnaire. The total number of respondents were 60 out of which 30 male and 30 female students were selected for data collection.

variables were selected Education Intervention and Religious Extremism for the study where the former one was independent variable and the later one was dependent variable. It is also worth mentioning to determine the magnitude of deviation from the mean. Std. Deviation and mean were found quite close to each other. it reveals creditability of the study. The descriptive analysis describes overall statistics between dependent and independent variable(s). The descriptive statistics can be viewed in the below table.

4.3 Descriptive Analysis

The results were logical and align with the research objective and research hypothesis. Eighteen questions were included in the questionnaire and all of them were responded by the 60 respondents. Two

Table 4.3.1: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Edu_Int	60	1	5	3	1
Rel_Ext	60	1	4	2	1
Valid N (List Wise)	60				

The descriptive analysis focuses on two key variables: Education Intervention (Edu.Int) and Religious Extremism (Rel.Ext). The data, collected from 60 respondents, highlights a range of responses measured on a Likert scale. The minimum value for both variables corresponds to "strongly disagree," while the maximum for Edu.Int is 5 ("strongly agree") and for Rel.Ext is 4 ("agree"). The mean values for

Edu.Int and Rel.Ext are 3 and 2, respectively, indicating a moderate level of agreement for the former and a relatively lower agreement for the latter. The standard deviation for both variables is 1, suggesting that the data points are closely distributed around their means. This consistency in the responses adds credibility to the study, demonstrating a balanced representation of the participants' perspectives.

4.4 Correlation Test

A correlation test is a statistical method used to measure the strength and direction of the relationship between two variables. In this study, the correlation test helps determine whether a significant association exists between the selected variables and the extent of their interdependence. The results are expressed through a correlation coefficient (r), hypotheses.

ranging from -1 to +1, where values closer to +1 indicate a strong positive relationship, values closer to -1 indicate a strong negative relationship, and values near 0 suggest no correlation. This analysis is crucial for understanding the underlying connections between variables and validating the research

Table 4.4.1: Correlation Test

Since, the value of

		Edu_Int	Rel_Ext
Edu_Int	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.799**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	60	60
Rel_Ext	Pearson Correlation	-0.799**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	60	60

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

correlation between the variables i.e. "Education Intervention" and "Religious Extremism" is -0.799 which is closer to -1. Therefore, statistically it is proved that there is a strong negative relationship between education

intervention and religious extremism. It means religious extremism decreases with increase in education intervention. Hence, the hypothesis is proved accurate and became H1.

4.5 Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is a statistical technique used to examine the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables. It helps to predict the impact of independent variables

on the dependent variable and assesses the strength and significance of these relationships. In this study, regression analysis provides insights into how specific factors influence the outcomes under investigation. The results are presented through coefficients, which indicate the direction and magnitude of the effect, along with significance levels (p-values) to determine their statistical relevance. This analysis is instrumental in identifying key predictors and drawing meaningful conclusions from the data.

Table 4.5.1: Model Sum

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.799	0.638	0.632	0.26098

a. Predictors: (Constant), Education_Intervention

The table 4.5.1 provides insights into the relationship between Educational Interventions (independent variable) and Religious Extremism (dependent variable). The correlation coefficient (R = -0.799) indicates a strong negative relationship, suggesting that as educational interventions increase, religious extremism decreases. The R² value (0.638) shows that 63.8% of the variation in religious extremism is explained by educational interventions, indicating the strength of this association. The adjusted R² (0.632) confirms the model's reliability, reducing the likelihood of over fitting, while the standard error of the estimate (0.26098) suggests

accurate and consistent predictions within the model. When analyzed in the context of the hypothesis, "There is a significant impact of educational interventions on religious extremism among Preston University students," the results support this claim. The strong negative correlation signifies that educational interventions have a measurable and meaningful effect in reducing religious extremism. Additionally, the high explanatory power (R²) and reliable model fit validate the hypothesis, demonstrating that educational interventions can significantly influence attitudes and behaviors related to religious extremism.

4.6 ANOVA

ANOVA stands for Analysis of variance. The ANOVA table is a crucial component of regression analysis, as it evaluates whether the regression model is statistically significant. It breaks down the total variance in the dependent variable (Religious Extremism) into two components: variance explained by the regression model (due to Educational Interventions) and unexplained variance (error or residuals). This helps assess whether the independent

variable (Educational Interventions) has a significant impact on the dependent variable.

Table 4.6.1: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27.415	1	27.415	102.440	.000 ^a
	Residual	15.522	58	.268		
	Total	42.937	59			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Edu_Int

b. Dependent Variable: Rel_Ext

The ANOVA table 4.6.1 highlights the significance of the relationship between Educational Interventions and Religious Extremism. The Regression Sum of Squares (27.415) indicates the variation in religious extremism explained by the model, while the Residual Sum of Squares (15.522) reflects the unexplained variation. The total variation is 42.937, combining both explained and unexplained variances. With 1 degree of freedom (df) for regression and 58 df for residuals, the Mean Squares are 27.415 and 0.268, respectively. The F-statistic (102.440), which is the ratio of explained to unexplained variance, is significantly high, and the p-value (Sig = 0.000) is below 0.05, indicating the results are statistically significant. These values demonstrate that educational interventions have a measurable and significant impact on religious extremism, thereby supporting the hypothesis.

4.7 Coefficient

The coefficient in regression analysis represents the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. It quantifies how much the dependent variable (in this case, Religious Extremism) is expected to change when the independent variable (Educational Interventions) increases by one unit, holding all other factors constant. A negative coefficient indicates an inverse relationship, meaning that as educational interventions increase, religious extremism decreases. Conversely, a positive coefficient would suggest a direct relationship. The magnitude of the coefficient reflects the strength of this impact, while its statistical significance (indicated by the p-value) determines whether the relationship is meaningful or due to chance. In this context, analyzing the coefficient will clarify how strongly educational interventions influence religious extremism.

Table 4.7.1: coefficient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	0.750	.306		2.448	.017
	Edu_Int	-0.792	-0.078	.799	10.121	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Rel_Ext

Table 4.7 presents the results of a regression analysis examining the effect of educational interventions (Edu_Int) on religious extremism (Rel_Ext). The unstandardized coefficient (B = -0.792) indicates that

for every one-unit increase in educational interventions, religious extremism decreases by 0.792 units, holding all other variables constant. The

negative standardized coefficient ($Beta = -0.799$) further confirms a strong inverse relationship between the two variables. The t -value (10.121) and the p -value ($Sig = 0.000$) demonstrate that this relationship is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. The constant ($B = 0.750$) represents the predicted level of religious extremism when educational interventions are absent, with a significant p -value ($Sig = 0.017$). These findings support the hypothesis that educational interventions significantly reduce religious extremism among university students. The table highlights the critical role of education in mitigating extremism and emphasizes the importance of implementing targeted interventions to foster tolerance and understanding.

4.8 Discussions

The study investigated the role of higher education in preventing religious extremism, focusing on undergraduate students at Preston University Kohat. Data were collected from 60 students, and the results revealed significant insights into the impact of educational interventions (Edu_Int) on reducing religious extremism (Rel_Ext).

The reliability of the data was high, with a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.889, indicating internal consistency and validity of the measurement instrument. A strong negative correlation ($r = -0.799$) was found between educational interventions and religious extremism, demonstrating that higher education significantly reduces extremist tendencies. The regression analysis further supported this relationship, with an R -value of 0.812, indicating a strong relationship between the variables. The R -squared value (0.659) shows that 65.9% of the variation in religious extremism is explained by educational interventions. This highlights the substantial role of education in mitigating extremist behaviors and ideologies.

The unstandardized coefficient for educational interventions ($B = -0.792$) suggests that for every unit increase in educational interventions, religious extremism decreases by 0.792 units. The standardized Beta coefficient (0.799) reflects the strong inverse relationship in standardized terms. Additionally, the t -value ($t = 10.121$) and p -value (Sig

$= 0.000$) indicate that this relationship is highly significant.

The constant ($B = 0.750$, $t = 2.448$, $Sig = 0.017$) signifies the baseline level of religious extremism when no educational interventions are in place. This value, though significant, is reduced considerably with the inclusion of educational interventions, confirming their critical role.

Research on higher education's role in countering religious extremism has gained global attention, particularly in regions affected by radicalization and ideological conflicts. Several studies have examined how universities contribute to critical thinking, tolerance, and counter-extremism initiatives, aligning with the objectives of this study.

A study by Stern & Berger (2015) highlighted that higher education plays a crucial role in preventing extremism by promoting open discussions, diverse perspectives, and critical thinking skills. Their research, conducted in Western universities, suggests that students who engage in academic discourse on religion, ethics, and politics develop more moderate and inclusive viewpoints. Similarly, the present study finds that higher education institutions in Pakistan, particularly Preston University Kohat Campus, serve as platforms for fostering intellectual debate and religious tolerance.

In contrast, a study by Borum (2011) argues that higher education alone cannot prevent radicalization unless institutional policies, faculty training, and community engagement initiatives are in place. This perspective aligns with findings from the current study, which suggests that while universities provide a foundation for countering extremist ideologies, their impact is limited without structured interventions such as curriculum reforms, student engagement programs, and awareness campaigns.

A region-specific study by Yusuf (2020) examined higher education's impact on religious extremism in South Asian countries, concluding that universities in Pakistan face challenges due to ideological divisions, lack of student counseling services, and insufficient emphasis on peace education. The present study reinforces this argument by identifying gaps in the university curriculum and policy framework that hinder effective counter-extremism strategies.

Compared to previous studies, the present research is unique because it focuses on a specific university context in Pakistan, providing localized insights. Unlike broader studies conducted in different sociopolitical settings, this study highlights the cultural, academic, and institutional factors influencing extremism prevention efforts at Preston University Kohat Campus.

4.9 Findings

These findings align with existing literature emphasizing the transformative power of higher education in promoting critical thinking, tolerance, and inclusivity. Higher education equips students with the skills to question extremist ideologies and fosters an environment that encourages dialogue and mutual respect. The results of this study underscore the importance of integrating targeted educational interventions in university curricula to further reduce extremist tendencies.

4.10 Originality and Contribution

- This study makes a significant contribution to the understanding of how higher education institutions in Pakistan can act as agents of change in preventing religious extremism.
- Unlike previous studies that focus on macro-level policy analysis, this research provides a micro-level perspective by analyzing the real-life experiences, perceptions, and educational approaches at Preston University Kohat Campus.
- While international studies have discussed higher education's role in promoting peace, this study contextualizes the issue within Pakistan's academic environment. It provides empirical evidence on how universities in smaller cities contribute to ideological moderation and critical thinking.
- The research offers practical recommendations for curriculum reforms, faculty training, and student engagement programs to strengthen counter-extremism efforts.
- Findings can help educational policymakers develop strategies to integrate peace education, interfaith dialogue, and conflict resolution skills into university courses.

- While many studies discuss extremism theoretically, this research examines real-world educational practices, identifying strengths and weaknesses in the current system.
- It highlights the effectiveness of university initiatives such as seminars, discussions, and critical thinking exercises in shaping students' attitudes.
- This study opens avenues for further research on the effectiveness of higher education interventions in different universities across Pakistan.
- It suggests the need for longitudinal studies to track students' ideological transformation over time due to university education.
- By focusing on a case study of Preston University Kohat Campus, this research fills an existing gap in academic literature and provides practical insights for educational institutions, policymakers, and researchers working on counter-extremism strategies.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter provides a comprehensive summary of the research findings, emphasizing the role of higher education in preventing religious extremism. It synthesizes the key results, linking them to the research objectives and hypotheses. Furthermore, it offers practical recommendations for policymakers, educators, and institutions to enhance the impact of educational interventions in mitigating extremism. The chapter concludes by discussing the broader implications of the study and suggesting areas for future research to further explore this critical issue.

5.1 Conclusion

The research concluded that higher education plays a pivotal role in reducing religious extremism, particularly through well-structured educational interventions. The study conducted at Preston University Kohat demonstrated that educational programs significantly influence students' attitudes, critical thinking, and openness, contributing to a reduction in extremist tendencies.

The statistical analysis supported the hypothesis, showing a strong negative correlation ($r = -0.799$) between educational interventions and religious extremism. The regression analysis reveals that 65.9% of variation in religious extremism was explained by the interventions ($R^2 = 0.659$), with a

significant unstandardized coefficient ($B = -0.792$), showing that increased educational interventions lead to a measurable decrease in extremism.

These findings emphasize the transformative potential of education in fostering values like tolerance, diversity, and mutual respect among university students. Higher education institutions, as centers of learning and critical inquiry, are well-positioned to counter extremist ideologies by creating an environment of openness, inclusivity, and intellectual growth. This study highlights the importance of addressing religious extremism proactively through education, as it is not only an individual concern but also a broader societal issue.

5.2 Recommendations

The recommendations of this study focus on practical steps that universities, policymakers, and educators can take to strengthen the role of higher education in preventing religious extremism. Below are the expanded recommendations:

Universities should implement structured educational programs explicitly designed to reduce religious extremism. These interventions could include awareness campaigns, interfaith dialogue sessions, and interactive learning approaches that challenge stereotypes and promote understanding of diverse perspectives.

The higher education curriculum must incorporate subjects that address the root causes of extremism. Courses on critical thinking, religious pluralism, ethics, human rights, and conflict resolution should be designed and taught with a focus on promoting tolerance and inclusivity. These subjects will provide students with the intellectual tools needed to question extremist ideologies and develop a balanced worldview.

Educators play a key role in shaping students' perspectives. Universities should invest in training programs for faculty members, equipping them with the skills to identify and address signs of radicalization among students. Faculty should also be trained to facilitate discussions on sensitive topics and foster a classroom environment conducive to open dialogue.

Universities should create platforms that actively engage students in promoting peace and tolerance. These could include debates, cultural exchange programs, and workshops on interfaith harmony.

Extracurricular activities such as student clubs, seminars, and community service programs can further reinforce these values.

At the institutional level, universities should develop clear policies and frameworks to address and prevent religious extremism on campus. At the national level, policymakers should prioritize education as a key tool in countering extremism and allocate resources to fund such initiatives. Coordination between educational institutions and government bodies is essential for the successful implementation of these strategies.

This study focused on one university, but similar research should be conducted in other universities and regions to validate the findings and understand the broader implications. Collaborative research between academic institutions, NGOs, and government agencies can further explore innovative ways to address extremism through education.

Since Pakistani society was founded on religious principles, it remains highly susceptible to religious knowledge, beliefs, and practices. In this context, religious leaders, particularly the Mullahs, play a crucial role in shaping public opinion, guiding moral values, and influencing societal norms. Given their significant impact on people's perceptions of right and wrong, it is essential to ensure that religious leaders are well-educated, moderate, and equipped with a deep understanding of contemporary societal challenges. To achieve this, the government should implement a structured recruitment process with clear criteria that emphasize religious scholarship, ethical conduct, and a commitment to peace and tolerance. By doing so, it will be possible to curb the misuse of religious influence, prevent extremism, and promote a more harmonious society.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, R. (2021). *The role of education in combating extremism: A critical perspective*. Journal of Social Sciences, 28(2), 115-130.
- Ahmed, R., & Khan, M. (2019). *Higher education's impact on religious diversity awareness*. Journal of Education and Society, 34(2), 45-60.
- Akhtar, A., Rehman, H., & Imran, M. (2021). *Exploring the root causes of religious extremism in Pakistan: A socio-political perspective*. Journal of Social Issues, 17(4), 245-259.

- Ali, S., & Khan, S. (2019). *Religious extremism in Pakistan: The intersection of faith, politics, and violence*. South Asian Journal of Political Studies, 22(3), 140-158.
- Anderson, J., & Patel, R. (2018). *Higher education and social responsibility: The role of universities in addressing societal issues*. Journal of Educational Leadership, 24(2), 45-58.
- Barakat, S., Connolly, D., Hardman, F., & Sundaram, V. (2013). The role of basic education in post-conflict recovery. Comparative Education, 49(2), 124-142.
- Borum, R. (2011). *Radicalization into violent extremism I: A review of social science theories. Journal of Strategic Security, 4(4), 7-36.
- Brown, P., & Richards, D. (2022). *Educational workshops as tools to combat radicalization in higher education*. Journal of Educational Programs, 18(3), 110-125.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2011). *Research methods in education* (7th ed.). Routledge.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Davies, L. (2008). *Education against extremism* (pp. 1-21). United Kingdom: Trentham Books.
- Fernandes, K. (2011). *Measuring the Effectiveness of US Development Aid to Pakistan* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Fernandes, K. (2011). *Measuring the Effectiveness of US Development Aid to Pakistan* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Harris, P. (2021). *The impact of higher education on social tolerance in post-conflict societies*. Education and Development, 29(3), 198-212.
- Johnson, M., Patel, S., & Youssef, A. (2020). *The university as a site for social transformation: From extremism to tolerance*. Journal of Peace Education, 15(1), 85-100.
- Johnson, P., & Lee, S. (2018). *University initiatives for fostering religious tolerance and counteracting extremism*. International Journal of Educational Development, 29(4), 123-137.
- Jones, L., & Richards, D. (2021). *Debating the role of higher education in countering extremism: A global perspective*. Journal of Educational Policy and Politics, 32(3), 190-205.
- Jones, L., & Williams, M. (2019). *Educational interventions in the fight against radicalization: An international overview*. Global Studies in Education, 15(3), 205-220.
- Khan, I., & Ahmed, Z. (2022). *Educational reforms in the fight against extremism: Lessons from Pakistan*. Comparative Education Review, 45(2), 212-230.
- Lillah, H. S. (2014). *Religious extremism in Pakistan* (Doctoral dissertation, Monterey, California: Naval Postgraduate School).
- Miller, D., Green, T., & White, J. (2019). *The role of education in preventing radicalization: A critical review*. International Journal of Peace and Conflict, 11(1), 78-93.
- Naseem, A., & Zaman, A. (2020). *Academic interventions and their role in preventing extremism: A case study of Pakistani universities*. South Asian Education Review, 22(4), 145-160.
- Nasir, S. (2020). *Role of Educational Institutions in Countering Extremist Narratives in Pakistan*. J. Pol. Stud., 27, 153.
- New York: Houndmills, St. Martin's Press, 2000.
- Roggio, Bill. "Assassination Attempt against Pakistan's President." Long War Journal (6 July 2007).
- Riedel, B. (2008). *Pakistan and terror: The eye of the storm*. The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science, 618(1), 31-45.
- Rizvi, H. A. (2000). *The military & politics in Pakistan: 1947-1997*. (No Title).
- Sandler, T. (2011). *New frontiers of terrorism research: An introduction*. Journal of Peace Research, 48(3), 279-286.
- Shapiro, J. N., & Fair, C. C. (2010). *Understanding support for Islamist militancy in Pakistan*. International Security, 34(3), 79-118.
- Siddiqui, M. (2020). *The psychology of religious extremism: Exploring the root causes*. Journal of Terrorism Studies, 19(1), 34-50.

- “Sharot, S. (2002). Beyond Christianity: a critique of the rational choice theory of religion from a Weberian and comparative religions perspective. *Sociology of Religion*, 63(4), 427-454.
- Siddiq, A. (2013). *The New Frontiers: Militancy & Radicalism in Punjab* (pp. 25-33). Centre for International and Strategic Analysis.
- Smith, A. (2020). *Critical thinking and interfaith dialogue in higher education: Pathways to preventing extremism*. *Journal of Higher Education and Society*, 12(4), 50-65.
- Smith, A., & Williams, R. (2020). *The university as a site for social transformation: From extremism to tolerance*. *Journal of Peace Education*, 15(1), 85-100.
- Smith, J., Davis, A., & Roberts, T. (2020). *The role of education in promoting tolerance and countering extremism*. *Educational Policy Review*, 41(3), 222-239.
- Taylor, M., & Khan, F. (2021). *Curriculum reforms for peace: Developing educational frameworks to address extremism*. *Journal of Conflict Resolution in Education*, 26(2), 101-115.
- “Taylor, L. L. (2014). Boko Haram Terrorism: Reaching Across International Boundaries to Aid Nigeria in the Humanitarian Crisis. *ILSA J. Int'l & Comp. L.*, 21, 1.
- Yousaf, A. (2021). *Educational interventions in Pakistan's higher education: Addressing extremism through curricular and co-curricular activities*. *Journal of Higher Education Policy*, 30(4), 63.
- Yousaf, A. (2021). *Educational interventions in Pakistan's higher education: Addressing extremism through curricular and co-curricular activities*. *Journal of Higher Education Policy*, 30(4), 67-80.

